

Modalities in Teaching, Assessment and Student Consultation in the New Normal: Challenges and Insights

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the modalities of teaching, the assessment tools, and the means of student consultation that the School of Education (SED) faculty used in the New Normal. This study identified the challenges encountered by the faculty, how they addressed the challenges and the insights that they gained from their teaching experience in the New Normal. The respondents of this study were the ten SED faculty; five were full time and five were part time. A survey questionnaire gathered the needed data. The survey contained eight questions, where three questions have indicators for the faculty to choose those applicable to them, and the rest were open-ended questions that allowed the faculty to describe their experiences. Frequency count, percent, and rank were used to analyze the quantitative results. The qualitative responses for the open-ended questions were categorized into themes. Findings revealed that Google Meet was mostly used by the faculty as their modality in teaching. Most of them used the assessment modules to evaluate their students' learning and they were alert on similar work output to ensure the authenticity of the work submitted by their students. The study also revealed that the personal attributes of the faculty were evident in their conduct of the student consultation, and in their ways to address the challenges encountered in teaching in the New Normal. Internet connectivity was the most challenging in the conduct of virtual classes. Furthermore, the personal attributes of the teacher "surfaced" in carrying out the professional duties in their teaching in the New Normal.

Subject Area

Teaching Modality

Keywords: *Teaching Modalities, Assessment, Student Consultation, New Normal*

INTRODUCTION

The teaching-learning experience for both teachers and students at this time is greatly affected by the global pandemic. When Covid-19 was declared as a pandemic in March of 2020, the Philippine government also suspended the face-to-face classes and the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) abide by the guidelines on flexible learning as set by Commission on Higher Education (CHED) as stipulated in detail in the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) of SIC as an Institution. The SIC's LCP in its Section 5 provided the Curricular Modifications reflecting Flexible Learning Strategies on content learning materials, teaching learning activities, requirements and assessment. With the challenges posted by urgent transition from face-to-face class to online teaching and learning, teachers commit to the demands of the time in the teaching profession. Modalities in teaching online have become the option. With this, are the challenges on the assessment of teaching quality and the assessment of the students' learning (Muller et al., 2019). According to Vonderwell, Liang, and Alderman (2007) the assessment of online and blended learning contexts have a difference in contrast to the assessment applied typically in the face-to-face modalities of teaching. Furthermore, the experience of this pandemic brought fear, anxiety, uncertainty, and indifference to some students, while there are also students who are able to adjust and did not get stuck. Teachers, being aware of this, continue to initiate means to help the students cope with their emotional response in their studies in the midst of the pandemic, where actual interactions with their teachers and fellow students are not possible and safe. Teachers demonstrate support to the students through the possible ways to connect with them (Loyola University Maryland, 2021).

Thus, this study explored on the teaching modalities, the assessment and students' consultation that the faculty of the School of Education used in their classes in the New Normal during the Academic year 2020-2021.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study explored the modalities in teaching, assessment, and student consultation used by the SED faculty in the New Normal during the Academic Year 2020-2021

Specifically, this study answered the following:

1. What modalities in teaching do the SED faculty members employ in the New Normal?
2. How do the SED faculty members conduct their assessment of the students' learning in the New Normal?
3. What strategies do the SED faculty members employ for the authenticity of the students' work or output?
4. What practices do the SED faculty members utilize for the student consultation in the New Normal?
5. What challenges do the SED faculty members encounter in their teaching in the New Normal and what remedies do they use to address the challenges?
6. What insights do the SED faculty members have in their teaching in the New Normal?

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on the premise that with the pandemic the education sector faces the new challenges for the urgent transition to online teaching and learning (Frolova, E. 2021). This transition from the traditional face-to-face classes to “online methodology” for higher education (Garcia-Penalvo et al, 2020) made the teachers learn the mechanism to transfer knowledge and develop the competencies needed by the learners with the online modalities in teaching with the concerns and challenges on assessment and student consultation. Figure 1 illustrates the schematic diagram of the study.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Study

Figure 1 illustrates the link between the Modalities in teaching with the Assessment of the Students' learning and the Students' consultation that the faculty of the School of Education employs in the New Normal. These modalities in teaching include the Blended Online and Offline modes of learning delivery. These include printed learning modules, study guides and assessment, and evaluation rubrics. The student consultation is a form of student-faculty feedback mechanism. At San Isidro College the faculty members are provided their space called “Online Teaching Learning Station” for them to conduct their virtual classes.

The third box reflected the challenges and insights that the teachers experienced. The New Normal posted not only the problems and challenges, but also the learning, insights and reflections.

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive research design (Best and Kahn, 1998). The study employed the survey method with the questionnaire as the instrument used to gather the data needed in the study. The responses to the questionnaire were also in preparation for the PAASCU visit in 2022 and in response to the Council of Deans of Teacher Education Region X (CODTE X) in the quest for the best teaching modality online.

The questionnaire has eight questions. Three questions have the enumerated items for the faculty to check those that were applicable to their modality of teaching. Added to these, were the open-ended questions for the faculty to give their descriptive responses. These questions were on the modalities of teaching, types of assessment, and the student consultations that were employed by the School of Education faculty. The rest of the open-ended questions in the survey asked on the challenges encountered by the faculty of the School of Education and their ways to address the challenges. The last question asked on the insights that the faculty have in their teaching experience in the new normal. The respondents of this study included ten SED faculty members, five of whom were full-time and five were part-time employees. The responses of the SED faculty for problems number 1, 2, 3 were tallied and ranked while the responses for the remaining statement of the problems were categorized according to themes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Modalities of Teaching

Table 1 shows the result of the modalities of teaching that the faculty of the School of Education employed in the New Normal. There are eleven (11) indicators. Based on frequency, nine (9) out of the ten (10) SED faculty used the Google Meet, this ranks first, followed by distance teaching learning where 8 out of 10 faculty used this as their modality in teaching, third in rank were synchronous online distance teaching/learning and modular teaching/learning. There were faculty members who used modular teaching/learning since there were also students whose internet connectivity was not stable. They preferred to have their learning materials printed out and their accomplished output or class tasks were sent to SIC.

Table 1. Modalities in Teaching used by the SED faculty in the New Normal ($N=10$)

Indicators	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
Distance teaching/learning	8	80	2
Synchronous online distance teaching/learning	7	70	3
Asynchronous online distance teaching/learning	5	50	5
Modular teaching/learning	7	70	3
Radio/TV Broadcast teaching/learning	0	0	0
Use of video	2	20	8
Google meet	9	90	1
Zoom	1	10	9
EDMODO	1	10	9
Facebook	4	40	6
Messenger	6	60	4
Blended learning	3	30	7
Khan Academy	1	10	9
You Tube	1	10	9

Table 2 presents the results on how the SED faculty conducted their students' learning assessment in the New Normal. The results reveal that out of the nine (9) indicators here, assessment through modules rank first with 9 out of 10 SED faculty who conducted their assessment in this way. This could be because the assessment tasks were just uploaded in the Google classroom and were easily accessed by the students with their SIC email account. This is also favorable to the SED faculty to monitor submissions rate of the submitted output and update the students with their performance. Second in rank was assessment through Google form where seven (7) teachers out of ten (10) used this in their assessment. Third in rank was the assessment through projects, assignments, portfolios and online quizzes where 5 out of 10 SED faculty employed these ways of assessing the students' learning. The result reveals that the faculty preferred the assessment that can just be done through the Google Classroom with students in their respective homes/locations. The faculty maximized the feature of the Google Classroom for lessons to be uploaded and the class tasks and other requirements to be submitted, rated and recorded.

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Table 2. Type of assessment used by the SED faculty in the new normal ($N=10$)

Indicators	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
use of paper-pen tests	2	20	5
through Google form	7	70	2
through emails/messenger/Instagram etc.	4	40	4
through modules	9	90	1
projects, assignments, portfolios	5	50	3
written reports, researches	4	40	4
journals	1	10	6
Quizzes online	5	50	3
Oral Recitation on line	1	10	6

Table 3 shows the strategies that the SED faculty used to safeguard the authenticity of the students' work or output. The results reveal that the entire SED faculty members were alert on similar work output. This ranks first among the eight (8) indicators. This implies that the faculty consistently monitored and checked students' work. Rank second was the checking of the material through the internet. This strategy of the faculty was consistent with the process to teach the students how to be scholarly and to use their critical thinking skills in the materials that they used for their class tasks, and to demonstrate their independent learning. Among the eight (8) indicators, matching the students' ability/skill with their work output ranked third. The SED faculty used this to ensure authenticity of the students' work/output. This implies that the faculty demonstrated their role that they know the ability/capability of their students in class. This also provided the opportunity to give the students the feedback on the impact of authenticity in the learning process.

Table 3. Strategies used by the SED faculty to safeguard the authenticity of the students' work/output ($N=10$)

Indicators	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
checking the material through the internet	9	90	2
being alert of similar work output	10	100	1
matching students' ability/skill with the work output	8	80	3
asking the student on the originality of their work	6	60	4
specify the task directions, criteria and expectations	8	80	3
request "honor code" pledge from students	4	40	6
encourage student's self-assessment, goal setting, and reflection	4	40	6
provide feedback every time along the way	5	50	5

Table 4 presents the practices that the SED Faculty employed for student consultation in the New Normal. There are four themes pointed out here that highlighted the personal attributes of the faculty in the practice of the teaching profession in the first and second themes. This implies that the traits of the faculty were evident in the conduct of student consultations much more in the New Normal where actual interaction between the teachers and the students is not allowed or limited with the pandemic. Student consultations have to be carried out as a support mechanism to improve students' learning process and eventually improve the academic response or performance of students in this new normal.

The third theme provided the need for communication that can be in other channels with the pandemic. Teachers made themselves available for their students to contact them and the teachers to connect with their students. The last theme specifies the scheduled consultation hours

of each faculty as reflected in the faculty work schedule. The students were informed by the faculty about the consultation hours that provided the venue for the students to contact their teachers for some concerns affecting their academics.

Table 4. Summary of the practices employed by the SED Faculty for Student Consultation in the New Normal clustered in themes ($N=10$)

Responses clustered into themes	Respondents	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
In the New Normal the SED faculty give students encouragement and inspiration	T1, T2, T 8, T10	4	40	1
Faculty exercise tolerance, compassion and openness	T1, T2, T 8, T10	4	40	1
Faculty are accessible through their Mobile phone No., Email, FB account	T3, T4, T5, T9	4	40	1
Faculty announce and serve their consultation hours	T6, T7	2	20	2

Table 5 presents the challenges that the SED faculty encountered in their teaching in the new normal. The responses are clustered in four themes. The result reveals that six out of the ten (10) faculty identified the internet connectivity and technical problems as the top one challenge since this affected also the other indicators like the attendance of students online, the delayed submission of output in the Google Classroom, the quality of teaching and learning and the giving of feedback online. The second challenge identified refers to the students' difficulty and adjustment in the new normal. There were those students who could hardly join the virtual classes that result to their submitted output that were lacking or not following instruction. Fabito et al. (2020) revealed in their study that internet connectivity is a barrier in online learning. Another study pointed out that students' readiness for online classes is burdened by the internet connectivity and cost (Yra et al., 2020).

Table 5. Summary of the challenges encountered by the SED faculty in the New Normal ($N=10$)

Responses clustered into themes	Respondents	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
Poor, slow Internet connectivity and Technology - technical related problems	T1, T3, T6, T7, T8, T9	6	60	1
Poor attendance of students online	T4, T6	2	20	3
Students' lacking attachments; Late submissions, Weak comprehension skills, Adjustment in the New Normal class	T2, T1, T4, T5, T10	5	50	2
Quality of teaching and learning, Lack of IMs, Adjustment in the New normal	T10	1	10	4
Giving of Feedback online	T6	1	10	4

Table 6 presents the recommendations of the SED faculty to address the challenges that they encountered in their teaching in the New Normal. The responses reveal their themes which included the ICT concerns, personal and professional traits of the teachers. Four (4) out of the ten (10) SED faculty revealed the traits the faculty have to demonstrate in their teaching in the new normal. Five (5) faculty cited indicators that were under the professional attributes of teachers. Two of the faculty cited on ICT concerns since online/ virtual classes were really affected by slow or no internet connectivity and some students also cannot upload/submit their output when the internet is not stable.

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Table 6. Summary of the recommendations of the SED faculty to address the challenges they encountered in the New Normal ($N=10$)

Indicators	Respondents	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
Faculty's personal traits: Faculty shows Flexibility, Innovativeness, Resourcefulness, Preparedness, Patience, Hope and Consideration	T1, T7, T2, T5	4	40	2
Faculty's Professional Traits: Faculty Monitor classes, Follow up students, Impose discipline, Prepare modules and alternative IMs	T3, T4, T6, T9, T10	5	50	1
ICT Concerns: Improve/increase bandwidth and ICT Maintenance	T8, T9	2	20	3

Table 7 presents the insights also of the SED faculty in their teaching experience in the New Normal. The result reveals the two themes under which the responses were classified. Rank 1 shows the personal traits that the SED faculty have considered and demonstrated in the needed adjustment for the teaching learning process in the time of the pandemic. The teacher is among the elements of the educative process as illustrated in the Acronym TEACH, where T – stand for treasure; E – empathize; A – accentuate; C – care and credible and H – Help (Serano, E. and Paez, A.R, 2015) the teacher's personal traits identify the good teacher that help the quality of education in spite the challenging situation of the New Normal.

The second theme was on the faculty's professional trait. The indicators reveal the interplay of the teacher, the students, and the sustained learning environment. Although the modalities of teaching used by the faculty have to fit the New Normal, the responses reveal that the faculty carried out their tasks in the teaching-learning process (Serrano and Paez, 2015).

Table 7. Summary of the Insights of the SED Faculty in their teaching experience in the New Normal ($N=10$)

Indicators	Respondents	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
Faculty's personal traits Faculty Show: Positive outlook, Compassion, Patience, Dedication, Alertness, Consideration, Persistence, Commitment, Resilience and Adaptability	T1, T2, T7, T9, T6, T3, T4, T10	8	80	1
Faculty's professional traits: Faculty: Engage students in learning Facilitate reflective teaching Demonstrate creativity in class and Sustain the balance- effective and efficient teaching	T5, T10, T8	3	30	2

Table 8 presents the best practices of the SED Faculty in their teaching in the New Normal clustered in seven themes. Four (4) out of the ten (10) faculty considered engaging the learners in their learning, as a best practice in their teaching. This is because the students benefit more when they take responsibility in their learning and the teacher only facilitates in the process. Learning is better enhanced in the context of cooperation and collaboration.

The second theme where three out of 10 faculty regarded as best teaching practice was on the use of the creative and alternative instructional materials that contributes to meaningful learning. It is good to note that although the other themes were used by one or two teachers only these indicators imply that the SED faculty were mindful of what works in the class (Serrano and Paez, 2015).

Table 8. Summary of the Best Teaching Practices of the SED faculty in the New Normal

Indicators	Respondents	<i>f</i>	%	Rank
Meaningful, fun, memorable teaching is sustained.	T1	1	10	4
Follow-up, Promptness and consistency are demonstrated.	T3, T9	2	20	3
Reflective teaching and learning are carried out.	T5	1	10	4
Student engagement, collaborative and discovery learning is facilitated, (SURF).	T10, T6, T7, T8	4	40	1
Feedback given to students helped.	T4	1	10	4
Creative and alternative IMs are used.	T5, T7, T8	3	30	2
Reading assignments greatly helped.	T2, T3	2	20	3

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS and RECOMMEDATIONS

The transition from the face-to-face classes to the online modalities of teaching brought about by the pandemic resulted to the flexible teaching-learning experience for both the teachers and the students. The School of Education faculty dominantly used the Google Meet as their modality of teaching. They maximized the feature of the Google classroom with the assessment modules to assess the students' learnings. They were alert on similar work output to ensure the authenticity of the students' submitted output. The SED faculty members were committed to extend support to the students as they made themselves available for students and to communicate with them. The teachers reached out to their student as a form of student consultation. The personal traits of the faculty were revealed in their way to address the challenges that they encountered in their teaching in the new normal. Their positive, resilient, compassionate, and dedicated traits surfaced.

The Best Teaching Practices and the Insights of the faculty were evident of the personal and professional traits that teachers needed most especially in the New Normal. It is noteworthy that the SED faculty demonstrated what makes the teaching-learning experience flexible, meaningful and sustained. With the birth of the New Normal in the academe, teachers need to reinvent new strategies and modalities that will create better ways of facilitating teaching and learning engagements in the virtual classroom.

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